

THROUGH THICKNESS COMPACTION RESPONSE OF 3D WOVEN REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Compaction characterization of fibrous reinforcements is fundamental to liquid composite molding (LCM) processes, where it determines the part thickness and fiber volume content for a given tooling. In this study, different architectures of 3D fabrics are considered. Single and multiple cycle compaction experiments were conducted on dry and saturated 3D preform samples. It was observed that z-binder yarns have a significant effect on the compressibility of 3D preforms. Three types of 3D fabric were studied, orthogonal, layer to layer and angle interlock, each having a different weave style and z-binder pattern. Orthogonal preforms were more difficult to compact to a target fiber volume fraction of 0.65, with peak stresses reaching up to 2.3 MPa. Cyclic compaction tests were conducted to highlight the importance of permanent deformation of the reinforcements to achieve high fiber content during an LCM process. The panels were infused with an epoxy resin and samples were sectioned for microscopy. The micrographs confirmed significant permanent deformation and nesting of the tows after compaction. This paper also presents a model to simulate and understand the viscoelastic nature of fibrous materials. The compaction response was modeled using a modified Maxwell model. Good agreement with the experiments was observed for all types of reinforcement. The data paves the ground for robust LCM processes in both simulation and real life.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid composite molding (LCM) is becoming one of the major out of autoclave manufacturing processes in industries such as aerospace, automotive and marine. In this process, liquid resin is injected inside a mold containing dry compacted fibrous preforms. This process is suitable for both mass and large volume production at lower costs, compared to other composites fabrication techniques such as autoclave curing. Another very important advantage is the ability to control fiber and matrix ratio efficiently by compressing the preform to a specified thickness. The mold clamping forces and preform's viscoelastic properties depend strongly on fabric architecture or structure, the stacking sequence and mold closing speeds. LCM has many variants e.g. in vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), the clamping force is applied using vacuum pressure under a flexible tooling. Therefore, controlling final part thickness is not straight forward as compared to resin transfer molding (RTM) process, where preform is compacted between two rigid tooling. However, VARTM is suitable for large parts where surface finish is not an issue. In both processes, the reinforcement compaction response influences the mold clamping force, mold filling and permeability. Therefore, it is vital to understand the compression response of reinforcements before fabrication.

Several researchers have investigated the compaction behaviour of 2D woven, braided, stitched, and knitted fabrics. Robitaille et al. [1] presented a comprehensive review of the compaction response of several textile reinforcements. Other investigators have provided detailed insights into the compaction behaviour for plain woven fabrics, such as in [2-4]. Several models were also proposed for modelling the compaction behaviour. The earliest model was proposed by Van Wyk [5], who studied

the compaction behaviour of wool fibers. Van Wyk assumed that the deformation was a result of fiber bending between contact points. Gutowski et al [6, 7] went further to develop Van Wyk's model. The new model was also valid for pre-pregs and considered the lubrication of fiber bundles. Robitaille et al [1] developed a relatively simple model, where compaction was modelled using a power law. Kelly and Bickerton et al [8, 9] studied the viscoelastic properties of glass fiber reinforcements during an LCM process. They observed that mold closing speeds have a great effect on peak loads and on relaxation after compaction; from which, they proposed a viscoelastic model for compaction, that is useful for any LCM variant simulation.

In spite of their impressive interlaminar strength and damage tolerance properties, few studies have focused on 3D fabrics. 3D woven fabrics have a complex internal structure consisting of tows in the warp, weft and through thickness directions. The internal fabric structure plays a vital role in determining mechanical properties and failure mechanism of a composite. Cox and Dadkhah et al. [10, 11] showed that yarn nesting plays significant role in failure under tensile loading with remarkable drop in elastic modulus in both weft and warp directions. In a later study, Mouritz et al [12] showed that resin rich areas between yarns spaces allow cracks to initiate and accelerate failure. It was concluded that different weaving styles result in variations in mechanical properties. Leong et al. [13] have studied the effect of binder yarn on tensile properties and failure of woven composites. Although there is significant work on properties and modeling failure of 3D woven composites, there are few studies available on processability of 3D woven reinforcements.

The development of permeability tensor with time and position, tooling design and simulation of manufacturing processes essentially rely on reinforcement's response to transverse loads. Recently, 3D fibrous reinforcements have contributed to open new composite applications for primary structural components such as aircraft engine fan blades. This type of preform has advantages over 2D reinforcements, in the sense that it provides additional through-thickness strength, improves the through-thickness permeability of the material and eliminates stacking of multiple layers. In this study, single cycle and multiple cycle compaction of three different types of 3D fabrics were investigated experimentally. Multiple parallel and linear Maxwell elements were used to model the viscoelastic stress relaxation data. Dry samples were infused with epoxy resin and sectioned for microscopy in order to investigate the internal structure and effect of yarn nesting during compaction.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Three different types of 3D reinforcements, supplied by Sigmalex, UK, were selected for characterization. It was expected that different architectures would exhibit different behaviour under compression loading. The z-binder yarns in all architectures have different paths or orientations to hold the structure together, see Figure 1. The preform details are presented in Table 1. Fabric A is an orthogonal fabric, having eight layers of warp and 9 layers of weft fiber bundles. One in nine warp yarns, there is an interlacing weaver with the rest of the warp stuffers. Fabric B is a layer to layer with six weft layers and five warp layers being the interlacing yarns. Fabric C is an angle interlock having eight warp layers and nine weft layers. One in three warp yarns is an interlacing weaver with the rest of warp stuffers.

Fabric Type	Areal Weight (g/m ²)	Warp Layers	Weft Layers	Uncompressed V_f
Orthogonal (A)	3353	8	9	0.37
Layer to Layer (B)	3045	5	6	0.35
Angle Interlock (C)	3260	8	9	0.26

Table 1: Details of the 3D fabrics

Figure 1: 3D fabrics with different architectures (a) Orthogonal, (b) Layer to Layer, (c) Angle Interlock.

2.2 Experimental Setup and Procedure

Dry and saturated compaction tests were carried out in a 150 mm x 150 mm square steel fixture installed in an MTS universal testing machine. In order to conduct reliable experiments, parallelism of two platens was ensured. The compaction loads were recorded using a 300 kN load cell attached to the universal testing frame. A pre-test was conducted in order to evaluate the compliance in the load cell and the fixture. The load cell was assumed to behave linearly with a constant compliance factor. In order to ensure that there was no movement within the system, two dial gauges were installed to monitor any deflection in top and bottom platens, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Compaction fixture installed in an MTS testing frame.

In the single cycle compaction characterization experiments, a compressive load was applied to 100 mm x 100 mm sample up to a set fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 0.65$), then holding the displacement to allow stress to relax for 60 minutes, this test being referred to as “Dynamic”. In the second set of experiments, compaction was carried out at five incremental steps of $0.05 V_f$ starting from 0.45 to 0.65 and holding the displacement at each step for 10 minutes. This test was conducted to determine the long-term relaxation behavior of the reinforcement, the test being referred to as “Static”. Multiple cycle compaction tests were performed to determine the permanent deformation of the reinforcement. In this test, the compaction was decomposed into two cycles; loading and unloading. The preform was loaded to a thickness corresponding to $0.65 V_f$ and was unloaded to its initial thickness and compacted again, the same procedure continued for 15 cycles until there was no major change in peak load. All tests were performed at a constant crosshead speed of 0.033 mm/s. Similar tests were conducted on preforms under wet or saturated conditions to simulate compaction during an LCM process. Hydraulic oil with a viscosity of 0.08 Pa.s was used as test fluid. The test fluid was used instead of the resin to

ensure that no curing occurs during the test. In an actual LCM process, the dry dynamic compaction represents mold closing and static compaction represents hold period when resin is injected and preform goes from dry to saturated state. The dynamic wet compaction is required in case of compression RTM where excess resin is squeezed out of the preform.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Single Cycle Compaction

These tests were conducted to determine time-dependent viscoelastic effects of reinforcements at the target V_f . The peak stresses required to achieve $0.65 V_f$ for each type of reinforcement under dry and saturated conditions are shown in Figure 3 (a,b). After reaching peak, the stress drops instantaneously and continues to relax until there is no further evident drop. It was observed that the peak stresses were higher in dry compaction than in the saturated condition, possibly due to fiber lubrication effects. When comparing three different fibre architectures, it was found that orthogonal preforms peaked at around 2.3 MPa whereas, layer to layer peaks were lowest among all having a maximum stress of 1 MPa. The angle interlock exhibiting an intermediate stress level of approximately 1.5 MPa. Figure 4 presents “Dynamic” and “Static” compaction curves, stress is plotted against V_f . The solid lines represent dynamic compaction (without relaxation) whereas each dot represents fully relaxed state of the preform at each V_f step. The compaction of fibrous preforms begin with gap reduction between weft and warp tows, once inter tow gap reduces, the tows start to flatten. This flattening continues until individual fibers are in contact with the neighbouring tows. The fiber lubrication effect was less significant in the orthogonal preforms, due to the stiff nature of tightly woven patterns of through vertical z-binder yarns. In orthogonal and angle interlock preforms, the tows did not expand freely, hence higher compaction loads were experienced. As a result, in an LCM process such as RTM, the orthogonal and angle interlock fabrics will require additional tooling or will compact to lower fiber volume content under 1 atm (100 kPa) vacuum pressure in VARTM. Looking at Figure 4, the maximum V_f does not exceed 0.45 in both orthogonal and angle interlock preforms at 100 kPa stress whereas, in layer to layer, V_f reaches up to 0.50.

Figure 3: Viscoelastic compaction response of 3D fabrics, stress versus time, (a) dry compaction, (b) saturated compaction

4.2 Multiple Cycle Compaction

In case of VARTM, the process is limited to vacuum pressure, stiff preforms may result in low fiber volume content in the final part. In order to counter high compaction forces, preforms can be compressed cyclically under controlled speed, displacement or force. In this study, loading and unloading speed was kept constant hence, it was not possible to determine elastic and viscoelastic components separately here, we are more concerned with permanent deformation. The remaining part of deformation is the summation of elastic and viscoelastic components. From Figure 5 it is clear that permanent deformation after cyclic compaction is much more than single cycle compaction, peak stress at final cycle being much less than peak stress at first cycle. Figure 5(b) shows peak stresses after each cycle ends. The results of the cyclic tests qualitatively reflect single compaction tests where orthogonal preforms require higher loads to compact to final V_f . As cycles of loading and unloading progress, the reinforcements reach a point where there is no significant difference in peak stresses and the cycles become repeatable. An example of the hysteresis plot is shown in Figure 5a which shows the shift in curves to the right which becomes diminished as the experiment progresses, and is negligible towards the end. This shows that the reinforcements reached steady state and no further permanent deformation takes place.

Figure 4: Dynamic and static compaction response of 3D fabrics under dry and wet conditions of (a) Orthogonal, (b) Layer to layer and (c) Angle interlock.

Figure 5: Cyclic compaction of 3D reinforcements, (a) example hysteresis of cyclic compaction of an orthogonal preform, (b) Cyclic peak stresses after each cycle.

4.3 Micrographs

To physically examine the microstructure before and after compaction, samples were sectioned and potted in epoxy resin. The internal microstructures of the samples were observed using an optical microscope. Three types of samples were prepared for each reinforcement, no compaction, single cycle compaction, and multiple cycle compaction. Figure 6 presents example micrographs of orthogonal samples. It can be observed that reinforcement compaction reduced gaps between fiber tows, in addition compaction also flattened and stretched the z-binder yarns at top and bottom while it bent and buckled the vertical strands, resulting in more efficient packing of fibers which reduced open channels for resin flow, hence lower permeability is expected in multiple cycle compacted preforms.

Figure 6: Example micrographs of an orthogonal fabric after (a) No compaction (b) Single cycle compaction, (c) Multiple cycle compaction.

5 COMPACTION MODELING

The stress relaxation was modelled using a system of springs and dashpots. Any linear differential model for the viscoelastic behavior of a material reflects some rheological model whereby springs and dashpots are connected in series or parallel. The spring is assumed to obey Hooke's law:

$$\sigma = E\epsilon \quad (1)$$

where σ is the applied stress, ϵ is the strain and E is the Young's modulus. The linear dashpots are assumed to obey Newton's law:

$$\sigma = \eta \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where η is the viscosity. These basic elements can be connected to each other in series or parallel. When the elements are connected in series, their stresses are equal and the total strain is equal to the sum of strains in individual elements. For elements connected in parallel, the strains are equal and the total stress equals the sum of stresses in the individual elements.

There are several models available in the literature that can be used to characterize the relaxation behavior of a viscoelastic material [14]. The simplest of these is Maxwell's model, which consists of a spring and dashpot in series. When load is applied, the initial elastic response can be thought as compression of the spring, and the subsequent reduction in stress can be thought as compression of the dashpot.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_s &= \sigma_d \\ E\epsilon_s &= \eta \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This results in compression of the dashpot whilst the spring returns to its uncompressed state. The rate of compression of the dashpot is dependent on the viscosity of the fluid in the dashpot. As the viscosity of a polymer is temperature dependent, the relaxation process also becomes temperature dependent, meaning that at higher temperatures, the viscosity of the polymer is low and hence the relaxation rate is higher. More details regarding the derivation of these equations can be found in [15]. However, the ordinary differential equation for obtaining the maximum stress is given by

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = -\sigma \frac{E}{\eta} \quad (4)$$

which has a solution;

$$\sigma = c e^{-t/\tau} \quad (5)$$

Where c is the relaxation stress constant and $\tau = \eta/E$ is the relaxation time constant.

In most cases, a single Maxwell element is unsuitable for representing the behavior of a polymer since the model assumes that the stress relaxes to zero after a certain time when the spring returns to its original uncompressed state [15], which in reality may not be true. However, the model could be modified to reflect the finite non-zero value of stress by adding additional springs and/or Maxwell elements to the original arrangement.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_t &= \sigma_{spring} + \sigma_{Maxwell} \\ &= E\epsilon_{spring} + \eta \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} - \frac{\eta}{E} \frac{d\sigma}{dt} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In this study, the experimental results were approximated using three Maxwell elements connected in parallel to a spring, giving a relaxation of stress as follows:

$$\sigma(t) = E\epsilon_{spring} + c_1 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + c_2 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}} + c_3 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_3}} \quad (7)$$

Where E is the modulus of the spring in parallel, c_{1-3} correspond to the stress constant in the Maxwell elements and τ_{1-3} are the relaxation time constants.

State	τ_1 (s)	τ_2 (s)	τ_3 (s)	E Maxwell springs [MPa]	E Spring in parallel [MPa]
Dry	7.7	7.7	76.9	1.3	0.8
Saturated	6.9	17.4	86.9	1.2	0.8

Table 2: Viscoelastic model parameters

The differential equations given in Equations (3) and (6) were solved numerically, using different viscosities obtained from a third order exponential decay function that was fit prior to the relaxation bit of the curve, to determine the relaxation times. Two different linear moduli were introduced, one to account for the single spring element and thus determining the stress relaxation limit, and the other two account for the springs in the Maxwell elements. The model is semi-empirical in nature. The Young's modulus E for the springs in parallel for all of the specimens were calculated in the linear region of strain over a time interval between 3 and 10 seconds. A third order exponential decay equation was applied to the relaxation curves at room temperature to obtain the relaxation time constants τ . These two stages were used to model the whole relaxation event. Assuming that $\tau = \eta / E$, the viscosities of the preform were calculated and used as input parameters, along with the modulus of the spring placed in parallel as well as those in the Maxwell elements to estimate the relaxation stress $\sigma(t)$.

The saturated and dry compaction results of the model for the orthogonal arrangement are compared with the normalized experimental traces in Figure 7. The single viscoelastic model accounts for much of the observed phenomena, including the initial compaction curve and subsequent stress relaxation. However, in the saturated case, the model under-predicts the relaxation stresses, reaching a constant value soon after 500s while the experimental curve is still relaxing. However, the predicted times for the material to relax are similar to those measured experimentally. This phenomenon could be due to the presence of the test fluid in the saturated experiment, and can be seen as increase in relaxation time constants, see Table 2. The slight decrease in modulus of the spring in the Maxwell's model for the saturated specimens indicate negligible decrease in stiffness of fiber preform due to the presence of the fluid. The stiffness of the springs in parallel that determines the relaxation of the material remains the same (0.8 MPa), indicating the process of relaxation to be similar for both cases.

Figure 7: Example viscoelastic modeling results based on orthogonal preforms (a) Dry compaction, (b) Saturated compaction.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A complete understanding of through thickness compaction behaviour of 3D reinforcements was presented. Three different types of reinforcements were characterized for compressibility. Experimental studies were carried out on orthogonal, layer to layer and angle interlock fabrics. An apparent time dependent viscoelastic deformation of 3D reinforcements was observed, which is an important information for predicting mold clamping forces and part thickness variations during an LCM process. Each reinforcement showed significant stress relaxation after compression to a target thickness. It was found that orthogonal fabrics were harder to compact at 0.65 fiber volume fraction, requiring 2.3 MPa stress. The least stiff was layer to layer structure, highlighting the importance of nesting phenomena during compaction. It is important to note that stress relaxation occurs over time periods on the same order as the full molding cycle. These reinforcements have been subjected to compression experiments in which common manufacturing parameters were varied.

The cyclic loading/unloading or multiple cycle compaction experiments produced more permanent deformation in the reinforcements causing smaller compaction stress than that measured during the single cycle compaction experiments. The micrographs have confirmed that permanent deformation has been shown to be significant in all cases, causing fiber nesting and flatness of the tows. Maxwell's model was used to model the complex stress relaxation process, which provides good fit to full range of compaction data for all reinforcement types. More accurate deformation models that can capture permanent deformation are required for further development of LCM simulations, allowing the computation of local forces acting on molds, and for some processes, laminate thickness evolution. This study is not only important to determine tooling forces during an LCM process, but also beneficial for mold filling and permeability investigations.

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